

Burnup Analysis Capability Based on Unstructured Mesh Geometry in Reactor Monte Carlo code RMC

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803233

ABSTRACT

Unstructured Mesh (UM) serves as an advanced geometric modeling method in Monte Carlo (MC) codes, offering inherent advantages for representing complex geometries, obtaining high-resolution tally results, and enabling high-fidelity multi-physics coupling. Although significant progress has been made in UM-based particle transport simulation within MC codes, full lifecycle reactor simulation still requires burnup calculation and analysis capabilities. The development of burnup calculation methods based on UM geometry in MC codes remains an area requiring further investigation. This study focuses on burnup calculation methodologies under the UM framework in MC codes. Leveraging the particle transport and tally capabilities of RMC's UM geometry, we have further implemented burnup calculation functionality based on UM in RMC. Both CSG and UM burnup calculation models of the KRUSTY are established for RMC. Results demonstrate consistent agreement between the UM and CSG models in terms of k_{eff} and the evolution of key nuclide masses across different burnup time steps, confirming the accuracy of RMC's UM-based burnup calculation capability.

Keywords: Monte Carlo; Unstructured Mesh; Burnup Calculation; RMC

1. INTRODUCTION

The traditional geometry modeling approach in MC codes is Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG), which utilizes surface equations and Boolean operations for modeling. Tally carriers can be based on cells or nested structured mesh. This technical route is well-established and has been widely applied with good adaptability in reactors with regular geometries, such as pressurized water reactors. However, with the ongoing development of advanced nuclear energy systems and increasing demands for high-fidelity multi-physics coupling analysis, CSG geometry demonstrates limitations in handling complex geometries, achieving high-resolution tallies, and facilitating multi-physics simulations.

UM is an advanced geometry representation widely used in fields such as fluid dynamics and structural mechanics. In MC field, Los Alamos National Laboratory in the United States has developed UM-based particle transport method for MC codes [1], implemented and validated UM particle transport capabilities in MCNP6 [2], and further established a multi-physics coupling analysis method integrating MCNP6 with the finite element code Abaqus [3]. These efforts laid the foundation for UM geometry-based particle transport in MC simulation and high-fidelity multi-physics coupling studies. Several MC codes have also conducted research on UM-based particle transport methods. For example, codes such as Serpent [4], RMC [5], JMCT [6], and NECP-MCX [7] have implemented UM-based particle transport functions through various means, including the use of open-source mesh libraries, mesh middleware, and independently developed mesh libraries. The aforementioned work has led to notable

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achievements in UM-based particle transport for MC codes, significantly enhancing their geometric modeling and computational capabilities, and broadening their scope of application.

However, for full lifecycle reactor simulation, MC codes must possess the capability for burnup calculation. The methodology for burnup calculation is relatively mature within the traditional CSG geometry framework. In the reactor Monte Carlo code RMC [8], developed by the REAL team at Tsinghua University, Dr. She built upon the point-depletion algorithm to develop DEPTH [9], a modular point-depletion program designed for complex burnup systems. DEPTH can accurately and efficiently handle detailed burnup chains involving approximately 1500 nuclides. By integrating DEPTH as an internal point-depletion solver within RMC, the integrated RMC-DEPTH burnup calculation capability is developed [10], establishing the foundation for burnup calculation within RMC's CSG geometry framework. This CSG-based burnup capability in RMC has been extensively applied and validated in numerous reactor benchmarks, such as the well-known BEAVRS [11-12] and VERA [13-14] benchmark.

To support full lifecycle simulation and analysis of advanced reactors with UM geometry, it is essential to investigate burnup calculation method and develop corresponding calculation capability under the UM framework. Although some researchers have explored UM-based burnup calculation method using MCNP6 [15], the computational efficiency reported in such studies remains prohibitively low. Therefore, MC-based methodologies for UM geometry burnup analysis require further research and development. Leveraging RMC's existing capabilities in UM-based particle transport and CSG-based burnup, this paper focuses on the research and development of burnup calculation capability under UM geometry, and the newly implemented capability will be validated and evaluated using a practical reactor model.

2. METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

MC burnup calculation involves a series of coupling of particle transport and point-depletion calculations. During the transport stage, simulations are performed using current material compositions to tally the neutron flux and cross-sections, which are subsequently passed to the point-depletion module. In the depletion stage, the point-depletion solver is invoked for each burnup region based on the current nuclide densities, power, and burnup time step length, producing updated nuclide inventory, which are fed back to the transport module for the next time step.

In the original CSG-based burnup calculations in RMC, the transport calculation is performed on CSG. In contrast, burnup calculations under UM geometry require the transport simulation to be conducted on UM. The current UM particle transport capability in RMC supports first- and second-order tetrahedral and hexahedral elements, covering commonly used mesh types and meeting the modeling and meshing requirements of practical reactor simulations. Additionally, the track length estimator can be employed to obtain high-resolution tally results at both the element and block levels. These established UM particle transport and tally capabilities in RMC form the foundation for developing UM-based burnup calculation capability.

Figure 1 illustrates the burnup calculation workflow under the UM geometry in RMC. While this workflow shares certain common components (highlighted in orange) with the original CSG-based burnup framework in RMC, the key distinction lies in the adoption of UM for geometry representation (highlighted in green). The main differences in the UM-based burnup calculation process, as compared to the CSG-based process, are outlined below :

- Modeling stage: Geometry modeling and burnup region division are performed within CAD software, where certain blocks are designated as burnup regions. These regions are then meshed, with material properties assigned to each individual region.
- Particle transport stage: The mesh file, containing both geometric and material information, serves as the direct input for RMC. Particle transport calculations are subsequently executed directly on the UM model.
- Neutron flux and cross-section tally: Within the UM geometry, neutron flux and cross-sections are tallied directly based on the UM model. These data are then passed to the point-depletion module to proceed with the depletion calculation.

- Material update stage: Upon completion of the point-depletion calculation, the material compositions corresponding to the UM geometry model are updated. The particle transport calculation is then performed again on the updated UM model.

Figure 1. Burnup workflow under UM geometry in RMC

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Modeling in RMC

The Kilo-power Reactor Using Stirling TechnologY (KRUSTY) [16] is a famous kilowatt-level heat-pipe microreactor. This paper selects KRUSTY as the computational case, establishes simplified UM and CSG models in RMC, conducts burnup calculation for each model, and compares the results and computational efficiency.

3.1.1. UM Modeling

This paper models the main components of KRUSTY, such as the fuel, heat pipes, reflectors, and shielding layers. Each geometric volume is meshed and assigned corresponding material properties, resulting in a total of approximately 1,430,000 tetrahedral elements. Figure 2 a) and b) present the CAD model and the UM model of KRUSTY, respectively.

Figure 2. CAD and UM model of KRUSTY

Appropriate division of burnup regions is essential for burnup calculation. The KRUSTY fuel features a quasi-cylindrical geometry, as illustrated in Figure 3 a). During modeling, the fuel is divided into 8 radial and 5 axial subdivisions, resulting in a total of 40 distinct blocks, as shown in Figure 3 b). Each block corresponds to an individual burnup region, yielding 40 burnup regions in total. These regions are then meshed, with the resulting mesh shown in Figure 3 c).

Figure 3. Division of fuel region

3.1.2. CSG Modeling

This paper establishes a CSG model consistent with the KRUSTY CAD model, employing an identical burnup region division scheme. The CSG model comprises approximately 100 cells. Figure 4 a) and b) presents the axial and radial plot of CSG model, with each cell distinguished by color.

Figure 4. CSG model of KRUSTY

3.2. Calculation results and analysis

For both the established CSG and UM models, identical calculation conditions are applied. The total burnup time is set to 500 days, divided into five burnup steps of 100 days each. The reactor power is set to 1 megawatt. Each cycle contains 50,000 particles, with 100 inactive cycles and 400 active cycles. Parallel computations are performed using 80 MPI.

Firstly, the burnup curves of the CSG and UM models are compared. Since the calculated k_{eff} at each burnup step have their own standard deviations, σ^{CSG} and σ^{UM} , they are combined into a single standard deviation σ , which is calculated by equation (1).

$$\sigma = \sqrt{(\sigma^{CSG})^2 + (\sigma^{UM})^2} \quad (1)$$

Figure 5 presents the burnup curves of the CSG and UM models, where the error bars on the CSG curve represent the range of 3σ . It can be observed that the deviations between the UM and CSG results at each burnup step agree well, demonstrating the consistency of the calculation results.

Figure 5. Comparison of k -eigenvalue between CSG and UM model at each time step

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the variations of ^{235}U and ^{238}U nuclide masses in the CSG and UM models during the burnup process. It can be seen that the differences in nuclide masses between the UM and CSG models at each time step are very small, indicating excellent agreement.

Figure 6. Comparison of ^{235}U nuclide masses between CSG and UM model at each time step

Figure 7. Comparison of ^{238}U nuclide masses between CSG and UM model at each time step

Table I lists the time required for the burnup calculation of the CSG and UM models, respectively. The total burnup calculation time of the UM model is 2.72 times that of the CSG model. It can be seen that the majority of the time is spent on the criticality calculation, while the point-depletion calculation consumes very little time. The time spent on the criticality calculation in the UM model is about 2.67 times that of the CSG model.

Table I. Comparison of burnup total calculation time between CSG and UM

Model	Total calculation time (min)	Point-depletion calculation time (min)	Criticality calculation time (min)
CSG	33.630	0.024	32.445
UM	91.590	0.024	86.628

Table II presents the calculation time of the CSG and UM models during the inactive and active cycles in the criticality calculation. The UM model took approximately 2.10 and 2.79 times as long as the CSG model in the inactive and active cycles, respectively. Since the active cycles additionally involve tallying neutron flux and cross-sections, the ratio of UM to CSG calculation time is higher in the active cycles than in the inactive cycles.

Table II. Comparison of criticality calculation time between CSG and UM

Model	Inactive cycle (min)	Active cycle (min)
CSG	5.576	26.869
UM	11.670	74.932

Overall, the burnup calculation results based on the UM model agree well with those of the CSG model, verifying the correctness of the burnup calculation capability in RMC using UM geometry. Although UM model may require longer computation time than CSG model, it is necessary to activate UM's burnup calculation capability when MC models must be described using UM and full-lifecycle simulation need to be performed. Furthermore, according to the efficiency analysis based on the KRUSTY benchmark adopted in this paper, the computational cost of UM is still acceptable.

Regarding the comparison of computational efficiency between UM and CSG, many factors can have an influence, including the intrinsic characteristics of the models and the methods used for their establishment. For example, in the KRUSTY model adopted in this study, the UM model is discretized into approximately 1,430,000 mesh elements, whereas the CSG model contained only 100 cells, indicating that the UM model is far more complex than the CSG model. In this calculation, the average number of neutron collisions is about 100, meaning that a neutron undergoes nearly 100 geometry tracking processes from birth to death, and the tracking process in the UM model is also more complex than that in the CSG model. These factors collectively contribute to the longer calculation time of the UM model compared with the CSG model.

A more comprehensive evaluation and comparison of the computational efficiency between UM and CSG, involving a wider variety of calculation models, is still under investigation and will be part of the authors' ongoing work.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigates the methodology for performing burnup calculation in MC codes using UM geometry. Building on existing research on particle transport in UM geometry and burnup calculation in CSG geometry within RMC, a burnup calculation capability for UM geometry has been developed and implemented in RMC. The KRUSTY reactor is selected as a test case, with both CSG and UM burnup calculation models established. Burnup calculations are performed under identical computational conditions, and the results demonstrate strong agreement, thereby validating the accuracy of RMC's burnup calculation capability using UM geometry. While the UM model required longer computation time compared to the CSG model in this study, the overall computational efficiency remains acceptable. Further evaluation and optimization of the computational efficiency of UM-based calculations represent ongoing work by the authors.

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